

Use of PIXE to determine the adsorptive capacity of a chelating resin containing 2-aminothiophenyl *S*-acetic acid from microwave digested solution of fly ash

M. Dutta^a, M. Sudarshan^b and A. K. Das^{a*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, University of Burdwan, Burdwan-713 104, West Bengal, India

E-mail : arabindakdas@rediffmail.com *Fax* : 91-342-2557938

^bInter University Consortium for Department of Atomic Energy Facilities, Kolkata Centre, Kolkata-700 098, India

Manuscript received 25 April 2005, revised 15 May 2006, accepted 17 May 2006

Abstract : The adsorptive capacity of the chelating resin containing 2-amino thiophenyl *S*-acetic acid, has been studied in the pH range 1–5. Microwave assisted digestion of standard fly ash (NIST 1633b) has been carried out and the digested sample has been allowed to equilibrate with the resin at different batch extractions. The resulting metals sorbed on the resin have been subjected to PIXE analysis, by using a 3 MeV proton beam, at a 3 MV pelletron. The exchange capacity of the resin, with reference to 15 elements have been studied, and the highest capacity has been found at pH 5. Complete digestion of fly ash can be used during sequential extraction procedures as well.

Keywords : PIXE, chelating resin, microwave digestion, adsorptive capacity.

The adsorption capacity of 2-amino thiophenyl *S*-acetic acid resin¹ has been studied, by adsorption of microwave digested solution of fly ash on the resin bed, and determining the pH selectivity of different elements. The aluminosilicate matrix of fly ash has been shown to be containing large number of elements². The NIST standard fly ash, NBS SRM 1633b has been used to compare the concentrations of various elements with the standard certified values. Complete dissolution of fly ash has been done using microwave assisted treatment. The method is fast, convenient and environmentally favourable, compared to conventional techniques of sample digestion.

In an earlier work¹, 2-amino thiophenyl *S*-acetic acid resin has been shown to be a good adsorbent of lead at pH 5, and the subsequent studies will show that it has selectivity for different elements in other pH values as well.

The adsorption capacity has been measured by proton induced X-ray emission (PIXE), a multi-elemental analytical technique^{3–5} where the 3 MeV proton has been used as a probe. Methods such as neutron activation analysis (NAA), X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy (XRF) and PIXE are complimentary to each other and can directly be applied to the solid samples for multi-elemental analysis. As the elution process is not used, the complications

of using an eluting agent is avoided, and the process is less tedious to perform. As such, they are found to be more beneficial for a solid matrix, compared to other conventional techniques. Besides, the advent of GUPIX⁶, a powerful software for data analysis has made this technique, an efficient one for the quantification of elements in a complex matrix, with high accuracy.

Results and discussion

The PIXE set up has been standardized by the NBS SRM 1633b fly ash standard. The typical PIXE spectrum of this sample is shown in Fig. 1. The results of standardization for the elements K, Ca, Ti, V, Cr, Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn have shown that the difference between observed and certified values is not more than 5%.

PIXE analysis : The analysis of the PIXE spectra has been done by the software GUPIX⁶. A theoretical spectrum, is at first modelled, using the data base of K, L and M X-ray energies, relative X-ray energies and fluorescence, which is then fitted with the experimental spectrum with respect to the known matrix. The software package provides nonlinear least square fittings of the spectrum, together with a subsequent conversion of the fitted X-ray peak intensities to elemental concentrations, via a defined standardization technique X-ray energy dependent H values, relative charge and user defined ins-

Fig. 1. Typical PIXE spectrum of NIST standard fly ash.

strumental constants. The software takes care of matrix effect, proton stopping power, X-ray mass attenuation

coefficient, and secondary fluorescence contributions for spectral fitting. The concentration of an element ($C(z)$) may be given as :

$$C(z) = Y_M [Y_t (HQ\epsilon T)]$$

where Y_M and Y_t are the measured theoretical and experimental yields respectively, Q is the real charge accumulated, ϵ is the detector's intrinsic efficiency and T is the transmission through absorber between target and detector. H value is the product of detector solid angle and charge correction factor³.

The sensitivity of the method depends on several factors, i.e. energy of the proton beam, nature of the target and background. The increase in background is highly unfavourable, because it reduces the detection sensitivity, as well as masks the weaker X-ray peaks completely.

In the present work, in order to reduce positive charge build up, graphite has been mixed with the sample, during target preparation. The H value and charge has been normalized for coal fly ash reference material by closely matching analysed concentrations with reported concentrations of elements present.

Fig. 2. Uptake of different metal ions by the bed.

Elemental analysis based on pH selectivity : Typical absorption pattern of various elements as a function of pH has been shown in Fig. 2. The adsorption capacity of K and Ca, are found to be high, at the pH range of 1–2, moderate at pH 3 and slowly decreasing with increase of pH to 4–5. Ti, Fe, Ni, Cu and Zn show high values of adsorption at pH 4 to 5 while pH 5 is shown to be the optimum for the adsorption of V, Zn, As and Pb. The adsorption of these elements are highly pH selective, at all pH lower than 5. The adsorption values of V and Cr have been found to be small at all pH. Ni and Cu have been found to show moderate adsorption by the resin. As the matrix is a mixture of various elements, in variable proportions, hence the adsorption of one element is affected considerably in presence of another. The adsorption capacity of Pb is found to be quite high for the resin, especially at pH 5. On the whole, it can be inferred that, except for Ca and K, the resin has shown moderate to good adsorption capacities for many elements in the pH range 4 to 5.

Experimental

Apparatus and reagents : 2-Aminothiophenol (Lancaster, UK), chloromethylated polystyrene resin (Fluka), lead nitrate and monochloroacetic acid (both from British Drug House, Mumbai) were reagent grade and used as provided. Synthesis of 2-aminothiophenyl S-acetic acid was carried out by the method as described by Mondal and Das¹. All other chemicals used were of the high purity available and at least analytical reagent grade.

The pH measurement was made with a Systronics 362 digital pH meter. A domestic Samsung CE 2933 microwave oven with a 2450 MHz frequency magnetron and 900 W maximum power was employed to carry out the synthesis of the resin and digestion of fly ash samples inside a home-made polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) reactor with 115 ml internal volume, 1 cm cell wall thickness and hermetic screw caps.

Microwave assisted digestion of fly ash and adsorption of metals by the resin : Standard fly ash NBS SRM 1633b was subjected to complete digestion by the microwave-assisted method. Initially, 100 mg in 1.5 ml HF was subjected to a power of 450 W and 4 min time, then it was subjected to digestion using the same power and 6 min time with 5 ml aqua regia. This step was repeated again. Then 3 ml of H₂O₂ were added, and digested for another 3 min at 300 W. Finally, 10 ml of saturated H₃BO₃ solution were added to remove any excess HF and heated on a water bath to reduce the volume.

The clear solution of the digested fly ash was now extracted by batch technique, by adding to 50 mg of the resin in a 50 ml beaker. 5 sets were prepared, and pH was adjusted from 1 to 5. About 6–8 h time were allowed to establish the equilibrium. After this elapsed time, the resin particles were filtered, and thoroughly washed to remove any adhering metal ion.

Target preparation : The metal adsorbed resin particles were dried, and crushed by an agate mortar and pestle, and then thoroughly mixed with extra pure graphite powder, in 1 : 1 ratio by weight (75 mg in each case). Thick targets were prepared by pressing these mixtures into pellets, each having 10 mm diameter, and 1 mm thickness, by a pelletizer. A similar pellet was prepared for the free (untreated) resin. Also for the purpose of standardization of PIXE setup, a pellet was prepared for fly ash (NBS SRM 1633b) using similar procedure as above.

Experimental set up : A collimated proton beam (2 mm in diameter with an energy of 3 MeV) extracted from the 3 MV Pelletron Tandem accelerator, at the Institute of Physics, Bhubaneswar (India) was used. The targets were mounted on a multiple ladder oriented at 45° to the proton beam axis and positioned vertically within the scattering chamber maintained at a pressure of 10⁻⁶ Torr. The targets were subjected to the proton beam for 30 min each, with a beam current of 15 nA, and the count rate was maintained at about 700 cps, to avoid pulse pile up. The characteristic X-rays produced from the targets were detected by a Si (Li) detector (EG & G ORTEC, having active surface area of 30 mm², a 12 μm Be window and resolution of 180 eV at 5.9 KeV Mn X-ray). The X-rays were made to pass through a 25 μm mylar window fixed to the detector port. The characteristic X-rays were recorded on a Canberra series 88 multi-parameter analyser in 2K channel mode. Prior to X-ray collection, the multi-parameter analyser has been calibrated with ²⁴¹Am.

Conclusion :

The results of analysis show that the 2-amino thiophenyl S-acetic acid can be well adapted for the multi-elemental analysis of a complex matrix like fly ash. The resin has been found to have a high selectivity towards Fe, Ni, Cu, Rb and Pb. By changing pH, the resin can be adapted for adsorption of these elements at suitable pH.

This work shows that PIXE analysis can be a suitable method for the analysis of chelating resins after adsorption of metal ions which excludes the tedious process of elution, by a suitable reagent. Hence it is believed, that it can be conveniently used, in place of other conventional

techniques of separation.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to the staff of Ion Beam Laboratory, Institute of Physics, Bhubaneswar, for their sincere co-operation during the experiments. One of the authors (MD) would like to thank IUC-DAEF, Kolkata Center, for providing fellowship in the form of JRF.

References

1. B. C. Mandal and A. K. Das, *React. Funct. Poly.*, 2002, **53**, 45.
2. A. K. Das, R. Chakraborty, M. De la Guardia, M. L. Cervera and D. Goswami, *Talanta*. 2001, **54**, 975.
3. S. A. E. Johansson and J. L. Campbell, "PIXE – A Novel Technique for Elemental Analysis", John Wiley and Sons, New York, 1988, Chap. 13.
4. Z. Dai, C. Ren, W. Ni and F. Yang, *Nucl. Instrm. Meth. Phys. Res. (B)*. 1995, **104**, 191.
5. R. K. Dutta, M. Sudarshan, S. N. Bhattacharya, V. Vijayan, S. Ghosh, V. Chakraborty and S. N. Chintalapudi, *J. Radioanal. Nucl. Chem.*. 1997, **221**, 193.
6. J. A. Maxwell, W. J. Teesdale and J. L. Campbell, *Nucl. Instr. Meth. (B)*, 1995, **95**, 407.